

Linguistics and Politics – strange bedfellows: an encounter, or a rendezvous, that, nonetheless, needs must when the devil drives!

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Resumo: Argumento neste texto que a principal razão do por que a Linguística encontrou, ao longo dos anos, dificuldades em lidar com questões de ordem política que envolvem a língua(gem), tem a ver com o compromisso que a disciplina assumiu de insistir em ser uma ciência, entendida nos moldes de neo-positivismo. Mas a questão de política está viva e palpitante, e continua a rondar o fenômeno da linguagem, talvez mais do que nunca, a despeito de toda nossa presunção ao contrário. O texto se conclui pleiteando que talvez tenha chegado a hora de enfrentar a questão política sem titubear e trazê-la para dentro da Linguística, ainda que isso implique rever a nossa forma de conceber ciência.

Palavras chave

Linguística como ciência – neo-positivismo – questões política – interesse público - relevância

Abstract: I argue in this text that the main reason why Linguistics has had a difficult time addressing questions of a political nature that involve language has to do with its inaugural decision to adhere to a conception of science forged in the neo-positivistic tradition. But the fact remains that politics is alive and kicking and continues to circle around the phenomenon of language, probably more than ever before, no matter how hard we pretend otherwise. The text ends with a plea to the effect that time may be ripe for us to face off the question of politics and bring it within the remit of Linguistics, even if it were to imply a revamping of the way we conceive of science.

Key words: Linguistics as a science – neo-positivism – political issues – public interest - relevance

Some preliminary considerations to start off with

Linguistics, the self-vaunted and widely hailed ‘scientific’ study of language, has had a trajectory of uneasy conviviality with matters that smack of politics in general and, more specifically, language politics. This awkward piece of truth comes to the fore every time it is called upon to address language-related issues of political import. Figuring prominently among these issues are those that have to do with language policy and language planning—as well as separatist movements in different parts of the world that typically revolve around the very identity of the language spoken in the area. All these topics of real-life concern are, needless to say, highly sensitive to the political climate prevailing at specific moments and the shifting sands of political imponderables. Typically, the linguists’ response has been one of unabashedly skirting the issue or unceremoniously passing it off as a nonissue.

That is to say, professional linguists have tended to systematically shy away from taking a stance on political issues relating to language, if only for the reason that they have an uneasy feeling that linguistics and politics do not chime with each other smoothly. And they are dead right on this, especially if we regard linguistics to be what it has traditionally been understood to be – the discipline, call it Old School Linguistics if you like — tasked with studying language scientifically and nothing else besides. Much like the way the biologist studies living organisms, or the chemist who concerns himself with the properties, composition and structure of substances. The more we ponder this puzzling issue, the more we are led to the unsettling conclusion that a good deal of this rather embarrassing state of affairs has to do with the discipline's rather obsessive claim of being a full-blooded science. Indeed, their very induction to the select coterie of linguists (as distinct from so-called 'traditional grammarians' and other allegedly 'half-baked' candidates to the claim of expertise on language) is conditional upon their having acceded to the unwavering affirmation that theirs is first and foremost a science. (cf. Rajagopalan e Silva, 2004).

And, under the rules of the game in progress, treating a field of investigation as a science meant, first and foremost, that there was no room for politics. Science is all about what and how things are the way they are; or, at best, about why they are the way they are - never about how they should rather be or how one might wish they were instead. And, let us remind ourselves, Modern Linguistics was born at a time when Logical Positivism reigned supreme when it came to the last word on what was to be considered genuinely scientific and what was not.

True to their early raft of convictions and articles of faith, the forefathers of newly forged the academic discipline were eager to relentlessly pursue their goal of being rigorously neutral on anything and everything that could be, in their view, 'tainted with' politics but for the cautionary measures put in place beforehand. With their declared aim of painstakingly observing and cataloguing given linguistic realities, the only subsequent step they believed fell within their scientific remit was seeking explanations as to why things were what they were, never taking sides on specific issues or weighing in on whether or not given states of affairs were welcome or salutary and could be traded for something better and more conducive to fairer results. And they systematically refused to acknowledge, against all evidence to the contrary, that the very phenomenon of language has an inalienable political dimension to it. Timely reminders such as that language is "a political-linguistic-rhetorical construct" (Joseph, 2006:20) were simply brushed aside.

So long as discussion stayed on the object called language (with no preceding indefinite article), that is to say, defined abstractly or generically, linguists could somehow foster the impression of steering clear of the political dimension of language and get away with the manoeuvre. But as soon as he or she sets out to identify living languages to be singled out, screened and selected for detailed examination, realization dawns on the researcher in question that there is no such thing as a language out there in the world ready to be picked up at their sweet will and pleasure and placed on, as it were, an operating table, in perfect condition to be anesthetised and pried open, in order to reveal its innermost secrets! This may strike some as somewhat bizarre, since many of us have long been persuaded to believe what we call language is out there in the real world, ready to be snatched and brought under the analyst's inquisitive scalpel. It is almost as though that, from the very fact that we speak of individual languages so routinely and casually, it should follow that there must be corresponding entities in the real world for them to refer to.

We need to literally invent a language before beginning to talk about it

If one comes to think of it, there are no such things as languages. That is to say, languages are not empirically observable, palpable objects that are out there in the world for us to grapple with, immobilise, bring under the scalpel. As the philosopher Donald Davidson

(1986: 446) famously said, "there is no such thing as a language, not if a language is anything like what many philosophers and linguists have supposed".

In order to conjure up a language, one needs to first reify it. Reification, or what we may vulgarly call 'thingification' is an act of "creating" something out of the blue, not "discovering" it. (cf. Rajagopalan, 2023). And it is only when and if one enquires into what factors are at play in creating those objects that one comes to the realisation that politics is first and foremost among them. This makes immediately apparent as soon as we move from language in the abstract or generic sense to language as a countable noun, individualised and named distinguishably. History is full of examples where the people inhabiting a given territory wish to separate it from the state to which it historically belonged and claim for it a separate and independent statehood—their struggle for independence all too often begins with the affirmation that they a language different and distinct from the language spoken elsewhere in the country.

What makes language 'x' different from language 'y' is that there are political forces that have, so to speak, conspired to make it seem different from each other rather than different manifestations of the same. Some years ago, the journal *Atlantic* carried a piece titled 'What's a Language, anyway?' written by John McWhorter (2016), where the Columbia university professor wrote:

The very fact that 'language' and 'dialect' persist as separate concepts implies that linguists can make tidy distinctions for speech varieties worldwide. But in fact, there is no objective difference between the two: Any attempt you make to impose that kind of order on reality falls apart in the face of real evidence.

But the fact remains that people, including apparently many a linguist, still entertain the belief there must be some non-trivial difference between a language and a dialect. And they appeal to criteria such as 'mutual intelligibility' and so forth that only help heap up more problems than they can solve (Rajagopalan, 2010).

The following case might help clarify the point made in the foregoing paragraph. India and Pakistan, two neighbouring countries in South Asia supposedly each speak a different language: Hindi on the Indian side of the common border and Urdu on the Pakistani side. At least, that is what each side claims in their official documents. The most curious thing is that, across the tense borderline that divides the two countries, people understand one another perfectly well and are, most of the time at least, quite happy with the way things are.

So long as the winds of political interests blow in the right direction, people forget whatever minor, superficial differences there might exist between their local ways of speaking and welcome positing a common language so as to cement a common bond. On the eve of India's independence from British colonial rule, faced with the impending disaster of the partition of the country, Mahatma Gandhi made a last-ditch attempt to promote a language he literally conjured up out of nowhere - a language he baptised 'Hindustani' which he hoped would accommodate both Hindi and Urdu under its umbrella.

Language as a politically convenient myth

That individualised, named languages serve the purpose of nation building and reinforcing nascent sentiments of a shared sense of collectivity is evident from the reference in the foregoing section to Gandhi and his unsuccessful efforts to salvage a nation from impending partition and breakup. No doubt, the very concept of language x, as distinct from language y, may well be traced back to a myth, but it is a myth that is immensely powerful as a rallying cry around which people are all too willing to gather in full-throated enthusiasm and spirit of self-sacrifice. It is not for nothing that people resort to the use of the term 'mother-tongue' (with all its associations with home, maternal cuddles, and so forth) to bring out their affection for the one language that they were first exposed to while they were in their cradle.

The fact of the matter though is that, while modern linguists have no problem recognising the power of the myth and enshrining it in the employment of the term 'mother-

tongue', they seldom go beyond paying lip service to the idea and explore how such deeply embedded feelings towards languages help shape social behaviour in later life and, in the end, affect language politics at large. All we can say by way of wrapping up this point and leaving matters as they are is that, for foreseeable future at least, this whole issue is destined to remain an embarrassing trade secret that professional linguists are doomed to live with for the time being.

The role of conventional (Old School) Linguistics in facing up to political challenges

But it is different issue when they are called upon to confront occasional language-related skirmishes that crop up in societies every now and then. The usual response, as things threaten to head towards a boiling point, is to duck the whole issue or brush it aside as long as they can. But, when matters show signs of reaching a crisis point, their well-rehearsed strategy is to argue that, as scientists, it is not up to them to weigh in on these issues. Or, alternatively, they are wont to come up with rather bizarre excuses such as that these are second-order issues that they would rather leave for professional politicians to tackle.

I have addressed some of these critical issues that came up during a cause célèbre in Brazil almost a quarter of a century ago when a politician and elected representative by name Aldo Rebelo presented a bill to the lower house of Brazilian parliament that, had it passed muster in the house and been sanctioned by the President, would have led to the enactment of laws stipulating serious restrictions on the use of "foreignisms" in the use of the nation's vernacular, Portuguese. and I will not repeat those arguments here (cf. Rajagopalan, 2004 a, b, 2005b) as it may veer us off the path we had initially set up.

Professional linguists and their dismal track record in addressing popular concerns

The only problem that behooves us to parse at some length is that, in so eschewing anything and everything having to do with language politics, linguists end up distancing themselves from the person in the street, preferring instead to conduct their high-falutin ruminations on the mysteries of human language in splendid isolation from the 'hoi-polloi'. As many working linguists have come to realise it sooner or later and at a heavy cost to themselves and their standing, this posture has not stood them in good stead.

As a matter of fact, linguists have had a rather ambivalent attitude when it comes to dealing with the common folk 'out there'. On the one hand, they need their help if only to furnish them with the raw material—the much-sought-after data—to work with; on the other, they are all too concerned about keeping the very same indispensable informants at arms' length, lest their own expert intuitions should get contaminated through contact with the natives and their folklores that are, in their view, the stuff of empty wool-gathering or, worse still, byproduct of pure gibberish (cf. Rajagopalan, 2017).

But, with the passage of time, more and more linguists have come around to the realisation that obsessive insistence on not engaging with the public at large on the latter's turf can only backfire in the long run. In fact, some of the damage may have been done already, as many ordinary people see professional linguists as scholars with lots of bookish knowledge about languages but with very little to say on matters of urgency and immediate relevance to their day-to-day concerns about their language.

Incompatibility between Linguistics (as traditionally conceived) and anything that smacks of Language Politics.

In the foregoing section, we have already touched upon the enormous gulf between the linguist and the lay person in matters of political relevance involving language issues. Now all these matters fall within the province what we may call language politics – an area that linguists have traditionally spurned and been averse to. It is almost as if they are convinced

that, by distracting themselves with these side issues, they may stray away from their more important objective of sticking to their scientific path.

But, as commented on earlier, such a 'standoffish' demeanour has only helped create an unbridgeable chasm between the linguist and the lay person. This alone should give us pause and ask ourselves if there are ways in which we can make our work as linguists to have a bearing on the lives of ordinary folks out there. Needless to say, the linguists will have to revisit some of their taken-for-granted working assumptions. Among these assumptions is the time-honoured goal of the discipline being a full-blooded science, along with the host of implications such a claim is supposed to entail. To begin, it may be worth asking ourselves what benefits would accrue from a suspension of the claim of scientificity of linguistics. What if, instead of viewing linguistics as 'hard' science of the likes of physics, chemistry and so forth, we start considering it on a par with, say, sociology, anthropology, and other human sciences?

'Hard' and 'Soft' sciences in their ability to address ordinary, everyday concerns, including issues of political colouring

Sciences, especially the so-called 'hard' ones, aim to come up with deterministic rules to explain the phenomena they aim to tackle. These are rules that operate infallibly. Once the preparatory conditions have been certified to obtain, the outcome is a done deal. Not quite so when it comes to what are somewhat disparagingly referred to as 'soft' sciences. Here the predicted outcomes are never a hundred per cent guaranteed. Soft sciences operate instead by the rules of thumb. They are heuristic, never deterministic. The best they can hope to be is to be explained, partially at least, by a set of stochastic rules.

In resorting to the use of heuristic and stochastic rules, soft sciences are on par with the rules of the game that govern politics. In politics what matters is not a collection of brute facts of the matter, and the conclusions one is entitled to draw from them on the basis of a set of well-tried logical procedures. Rather, we are in a terrain where decisions are made on the strength of one's 'gut feeling' or 'horse sense' or whatever one might wish to call it. Here familiarity with the terrain and lessons learned from past experience count a lot more than cold, logical thinking. Instead of what we referred to earlier as 'brute facts of the matter' one is required to deal with how facts are viewed by the public at large. And, needless to say, also, how those facts are spun and presented to the public.

From the brief discussion above, it should be fairly evident that hard science is of little help when one is playing politics. Linguists have had a difficult time coming to recognise this simple truism and many try in vain to convince themselves that their professional training and years of field work entitles them to have a privileged say in matters of language politics. Nothing could be further from the truth, as I showed in a lengthy discussion of the topic in Rajagopalan (2004).

Given the current dilemma what can the linguist do if they wish to intervene in language politics?

It must be fairly evident from the discussion thus far that the principal reason why linguists have a hard time bringing the weight of their opinions to bear on the way language politics is played out in society is that their hands are, so to speak, tied in respect of their ability to do so, thanks to an inaugural decision on the part of the founders of the discipline not to have any trucks with questions of politics. The crucial question that we need to ask and find an answer to is: what if we let go of that article of faith and choose to recognise that there is an inalienable political dimension to language?

Another way of posing the question in even starker terms would be: Is it possible that a linguist considers it legitimate to ask questions of a political nature with respect to the language that is in their focus, without thereby relinquishing their claims to being an expert –

with the title of a scientist - on language? Knowing full well that I may well be facing a storm of protest from my 'disciplinary' brethren, I venture to submit that there is nothing wrong or scandalous about knocking off an assumption that has only hindered genuine progress in the field, preventing researchers from asking important questions that public would love to see properly addressed.

Linguistics and the urgent need to look beyond

In end, it all boils down to a question of choice. Do we insist on sticking to the intellectual climate, along with its dictates on what counts as a respectable field of study, that prevailed at the time when the early pioneers of the discipline we now call 'Linguistics' worked under? Or should we instead be concentrating more on evolving steadily into a group of researchers genuinely interested in making our efforts more geared towards the needs and aspirations of those who are, one way or another, at the receiving end of those efforts? If our choice is in favour of the first option, we may very well end up not letting ourselves be bothered about the end results of our researches, solely interested in doing something along the lines of science for science's sake!

On a personal note, the present author is of the opinion that research that does not contemplate the well being and the betterment of those within its remit is nothing short of time wasted. Reimer (2016) struck the right note when he pointed out that

Linguists have, in fact, on the whole been strikingly reluctant to direct against their own discipline the kinds of critique that swept over the rest of the humanities in the final third of the last century. Linguistics' scientific pretensions act as a strong brake on any attempt even to think in critical terms about the epistemic status of the discipline's results, let alone to explore the field's wider political effects or determinants.

The fact remains, however, that, perhaps unbeknownst to themselves, their work has served the interests of the State and other powers that be. As Hutton (2020: 33) puts it bluntly: "[...] throughout modern Western history the state has made use of the study of linguistics." And he goes to elaborate the point by saying:

States have strategic interests in the production of particular forms of knowledge, though there is no guarantee that the knowledge produced will be directly useful or reducible to policy goals. The study of non-European languages, the development of writings systems, nomenclatures, and typological classifications, went hand-in-hand with the formalization of European empires, but the imperial project was itself internally conflicted about its methods, aims, and institutions. (Hutton, 2020: 33)

Hutton is making a very important point here. What he is alluding to is that, whether or not we are actually cognizant of it, our researches are always being used to serve this or that political agenda. That is to say, the researchers themselves might sincerely believe their work is innocent of any ideological connotations, but their work can serve a political agenda in ways undreamt of by them.

By way of rounding off our discussion

In light of the discussion in the foregoing sections of the paper, we linguists need to make a crucial decision in respect of our future conduct. Maybe the time has come for us to recognise once and for all that the issue of language has always been and will always be enmeshed in politics. It is pointless and perverse to pretend otherwise. The earlier we acted upon this recognition, the better our chances of saving our discipline from its self-imposed isolation from mundane language-related problems that ordinary folks have had to deal with on their own. This will not only render the much-needed dose of enthusiasm that the field has

been clamouring for, but also pave the way for making our making our research more user-oriented and relevant to their needs and aspirations.

On a more upbeat note, we might conclude our discussion by noting that, nowadays, more and more scholars are beginning to find it reasonable that we pair Linguistics with Politics, in ways that would have raised many an eyebrow in the not remote past. This alone should give us some justification for getting excited about future prospects since there can be no doubt that what lies ahead is a vast, as-yet-unexplored, terrain where significant research into how languages play a vital part in bringing people together or, contrariwise, in pulling them apart from one another by erecting imaginary barriers deemed insurmountable — so much as that it becomes well-nigh-impossible to talk about one without mentioning the other in the same breath.

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